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Abstract: *The study assesses the role of Christian Religious Studies Students (CRS) in social implication of HIV/AIDS on intervention for learning disability of CRS in senior secondary schools, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The objective of the study is to assess the role of CRS in social implications of HIV/AIDS infections on the lives of Senior Secondary School CRS Students of learning disability. The study adopted survey research design, specifically, descriptive method. The population of the study comprised of Christian Religious Studies students in senior secondary schools in Nasarawa state. The total population is made up of 17,854. Nine hundred and sixty (960) respondents were randomly sampled to represent the total population. One instrument was employed to collect data, namely, questionnaire. The finding revealed that, Christian education plays a vital role in the social implications of HIV/AIDS on the social lives of CRS Senior Secondary School Students of learning disability living with HIV/AIDS by creating more awareness on the disease because their lives are affected since students are scared of eating together and attending cultural activities organized by the school with them. The study recommends that, CRS teachers should frequently organize counselling on HIV/AIDS awareness among learning disabilities and rehabilitation CRS Students in order to curb prevalence of the disease. Christian leaders too should assist in creating awareness in the Church and society among CRS learning disability students on transmission and prevention of HIV/AIDS so as to curb the negative social implication perceived in Senior Secondary Schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.*

Keywords: Disability CRS Students, Social Implications, HIV/AIDSs, Intervention, Role

Introduction

Social issues are central to the transformation and development of human society, particularly in shaping interpersonal relationships, social interactions, and the overall well-being of individuals. They encompass conditions and circumstances that influence how individuals relate within a community and how such relationships contribute to societal stability and progress. Social issues, therefore, are not only reflections of societal realities but also determinants of the quality of life experienced by individuals across different phases of development. Human society is dynamic and subject to continuous change, which may be positive or negative depending on prevailing socio-cultural, economic, and health-related factors.

One of the most significant social and health challenges affecting contemporary society is the spread of Human Immunodeficiency Virus/Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (HIV/AIDS). Over the years, HIV/AIDS has profoundly altered social interactions, relationships, and patterns of behaviour, particularly among young people and students. In many communities, including Nasarawa State, the disease has contributed to fear, stigma, and discrimination, thereby disrupting normal social engagement. For instance, students often avoid sharing meals, participating in group activities, or engaging in close interpersonal relationships with individuals perceived to be living with HIV/AIDS. Such behaviours have led to a decline in social cohesion and interpersonal relationships within educational settings (Wyke, 2015; Loserian & Jeckoniah, 2018; Usadolo, 2019; Entonu & Agwale, 2019).

The stigmatization associated with HIV/AIDS remains one of the most pervasive social implications of the disease. Awofala and Ogundele (2020) observed that a significant proportion of individuals living with HIV/AIDS experience social rejection and marginalization, with approximately 65% reporting some form of stigma. This stigmatization manifests in various forms, including avoidance, exclusion from social and academic activities, and negative labeling. Lutala (2019) further emphasized that such negative attitudes are often rooted in misconceptions about the disease, leading to the erroneous belief that HIV/AIDS is a death sentence or a moral failing.

In addition, the lack of social support and empathy for individuals living with HIV/AIDS has contributed to increased psychological distress and social isolation. Dosso (2021) and Nsubuga (2024) noted that limited visitation and support for affected individuals often result in emotional trauma and, in some cases, premature death. Victims are frequently denied equal treatment within families, churches, and communities, leading to feelings of inferiority and alienation. Kuete (2024) also affirmed that HIV/AIDS has weakened social bonds, as individuals increasingly withdraw from interactions with affected persons due to fear and ignorance.

However, it is important to note that not all social outcomes associated with HIV/AIDS are negative. Wansijiru and Tera (2025) reported that, in some cases, individuals living with HIV/AIDS have formed supportive relationships, including marriages, which have contributed to their emotional stability and well-being. These findings suggest that with proper awareness and support, individuals affected by HIV/AIDS can lead fulfilling and socially integrated lives.

Globally, health organizations such as the World Health Organization have emphasized that HIV/AIDS is not merely a medical condition but a social phenomenon influenced by cultural, economic, and behavioural factors. The epidemic is shaped by social processes such as poverty, unemployment, gender inequality, and cultural norms, which create conditions of vulnerability and risk. In regions such as sub-Saharan Africa, rapid social changes, including urbanization, globalization,

and shifting family structures, have contributed to the spread of HIV/AIDS. These dynamics highlight the need for holistic approaches that address both the medical and social dimensions of the disease.

In the context of education, the impact of HIV/AIDS extends beyond health to affect learning outcomes, particularly among students with learning disabilities. Learning disabilities are often exacerbated by social exclusion, emotional distress, and lack of support, all of which are common among students affected by HIV/AIDS. In Nasarawa State, students studying Christian Religious Studies (CRS) are not exempt from these challenges. Negative perceptions, stigma, and misinformation about HIV/AIDS can hinder their academic performance, social integration, and overall development.

Christian education, particularly through CRS, plays a vital role in shaping the moral, spiritual, and social values of students. It provides a platform for addressing societal issues, promoting empathy, and fostering inclusive attitudes. Biblical teachings emphasize love, compassion, forgiveness, and care for others, which are essential in addressing the stigma associated with HIV/AIDS. For instance, biblical passages such as Psalm 103:2–3 highlight God's healing power, while 2 Corinthians 12:7–9 emphasizes the significance of grace and strength in times of weakness. These teachings can be used to reshape students' perceptions and attitudes toward individuals living with HIV/AIDS.

The Bible also contains several references to incurable diseases, which are sometimes interpreted as metaphors for spiritual conditions or consequences of human actions. For example, Deuteronomy 28:27, 35 associates certain diseases with disobedience, while passages such as Job 2:7 describe severe physical afflictions. However, such interpretations have been widely debated among scholars. Mkhize (2022) argued that biblical texts are often subject to diverse interpretations, which may influence how individuals perceive diseases such as HIV/AIDS. Some view the disease as a punishment from God, while others attribute it to satanic influence or consider it a test of faith.

These differing perspectives have significant implications for how individuals living with HIV/AIDS are treated within Christian communities. Misinterpretations of biblical teachings can reinforce stigma and discrimination, whereas informed and compassionate interpretations can promote acceptance and support. For instance, the story of Job illustrates that suffering is not always a result of wrongdoing but may serve a greater purpose. Similarly, the narrative of Lazarus demonstrates that illness does not diminish one's relationship with God.

The issue of stigma is further reflected in biblical lamentations such as Psalm 22, where the Psalmist expresses feelings of abandonment and isolation. Goffman (2021) related these experiences to the social realities of individuals living with HIV/AIDS, who often feel neglected and marginalized. However, the Psalm also emphasizes the role of community and faith in overcoming despair, suggesting that supportive social structures are essential for rehabilitation. In contrast, some scholars argue that increased awareness and government interventions have reduced stigma in recent years. Ndamson (2022) and Magaji (2023) contended that sensitization programmes and support initiatives in Nigeria have improved public attitudes toward HIV/AIDS, making stigmatization less justifiable. Despite these efforts, negative perceptions persist, particularly among students, indicating the need for continuous education and intervention.

The Nigerian National Policy on Education underscores the importance of education as a tool for national development and social transformation. It emphasizes the need for curricula that promote values, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills. Within this framework, Christian Religious Education has a unique role in addressing social issues such as HIV/AIDS by fostering moral development and social responsibility. Innovative teaching approaches, such as the psycho-social

method advocated by Senge (1994), can enhance the effectiveness of CRS in addressing HIV/AIDS-related issues. This method encourages active participation, critical reflection, and problem-solving, enabling students to engage deeply with societal challenges. By incorporating such approaches, CRS can contribute to the rehabilitation of students affected by HIV/AIDS and those with learning disabilities.

Furthermore, teachers of Christian Religious Studies play a crucial role as facilitators of learning and agents of social change. They are expected to create inclusive learning environments that respect the dignity and worth of every student, regardless of health status or ability. By promoting values such as empathy, tolerance, and mutual respect, teachers can help reduce stigma and foster positive social interactions. In addition, there is a need to shift the focus of education from mere cognitive achievement to the development of attitudes and values that support social integration and rehabilitation. Students should be equipped with the skills and knowledge necessary to address societal challenges, including those related to HIV/AIDS. This includes fostering critical thinking, encouraging open dialogue, and promoting evidence-based understanding of the disease.

In conclusion, the social implications of HIV/AIDS in Nasarawa State present significant challenges for students, particularly those with learning disabilities. However, Christian education offers a powerful tool for addressing these challenges by promoting positive values, reducing stigma, and supporting rehabilitation. Through effective teaching, curriculum development, and community engagement, CRS can play a transformative role in enhancing the well-being and social integration of students affected by HIV/AIDS.

Statement of the Problem

HIV/AIDS is among the deadly diseases bringing setbacks to students and causing their health challenges in post-primary schools in Nasarawa State. It is one of the most devastating diseases humanities has ever faced. HIV/AIDS has become a significant public health challenge, which has caused concern among many, as new infections are occurring in young students daily in Nasarawa State senior secondary schools. Students at this level face the risk of HIV/AIDS infection. This is as a result of their high risk in sexual urge behaviours that lead them into unprotected sexual practice.

About 1,086 senior secondary school students in Nasarawa state between the ages of 14 and 1 were counselled and tested with HIV/AIDS and have been confirmed to be carrying the deadly virus. In 2016, about 240,000 adolescents between the ages of 10 and 19 were living with HIV/AIDS related diseases in Nigerian secondary schools, thereby making up 7% of the number of people living with the virus in Nigeria. HIV prevalence among this age group varies regionally, with 4.3% of 15-19 year-olds living with HIV in Nasarawa State, Nigeria (UNICEF, 2024).

Objective of the Study

The specific objective of the study is:

1. to assess the social implication of HIV/AIDS infection on Christian Religious Studies learning disability students in Senior Secondary School Students in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.
2. identify the HIV/AIDS-related social challenges influence the academic participation and learning outcomes of CRS students with learning disabilities?

Research Question

1. What is the social implication of HIV/AIDS infection on Christian Religious Studies learning disability students in Senior Secondary School Students in Nasarawa State, Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference among Christian Religious Studies learning disability students in their social lives toward those living with HIV/AIDS infection and its social implication on Senior Secondary School Students in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopts descriptive survey research design. This allows for the systematic collection of data from a sample of the population and explains the conditions of the study by using a large number of subjects and a questionnaire (Carrol, 2023). The choice of survey design method aligns with the suitability and reliability in testing facts that provide insight and could be of benefit to other researchers.

Population

The population for this study comprised all Christian Religious Studies students in senior secondary schools, both male and female, from SSI to SSIII, in rural and urban areas of Nasarawa State. The state is made up of three senatorial districts: Nasarawa West Senatorial District, made up of five (5) local government areas, North Central Senatorial District, comprised of three (3) local government areas, and Nasarawa South Senatorial District, made up of five (5) local government areas. Based on the three senatorial districts, the state has thirteen (13) local government areas. In these LGAs, there is a total population of seventeen thousand, eight hundred and fifty-four (17,854) Christian Religious Studies students (Ministry of Education, Lafia, 2023).

Sample and Sampling Technique

Eight (8) LGAs that made up Nasarawa state Nigeria. A simple random sample population of 960 respondents out of the total population of 17,854 is used for the study. A structured questionnaire was the instrument employed for data collection. The data analyses were based on the responses from 960 respondents out of the sampled 1,098 students. The respondents are randomly selected from 8 LGAs in 3 senatorial districts from 32 schools that were prone to HIV/AIDS cases. The vetted questionnaire was administered by the researcher with the help of 3 research assistants. The data was analyzed using Version 20 of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Frequencies and simple percentages were used for demographic variables, mean scores for the items were based on four-point Likert scale and the midpoint average for decision for items or variables was fixed at 2.50 while independent sample t-test for testing the hypothesis at 0.05 levels of significance. This implies that, a mean score of 2.50 and above indicates agreement (positive response) with the suggested notion of items while mean score of below 2.50 implies disagreement (negative response).

Instrumentation

In this study, the researcher used one (1) instrument, namely, a questionnaire. The researcher constructed the instruments using insights gained from the literature related to the study and its specific objectives. The questionnaire was used to gather information from the respondents on the subject matter. The instruments were developed based the study's objective and reviewed literature. The instruments were validated following the ability to measure what was purported to measure. Since both values of 0.808 were closer to 1, it was deemed to be very reliable and therefore suitable for the main study. The number of copies of the questionnaire administered to each of the thirty-two (32) schools under study was thirty-six (36). After administering the questionnaire with the help of research assistants, the researcher waited to collect the completed copies immediately.

The data collected were computed and analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. The analysis of data for this study was done based on the research questions and hypotheses. Descriptive data analyses were presented. Frequency and simple percentages were used to present demographic variables in the study, while means and standard deviations were employed to answer the research questions. The null hypothesis was tested using independent sample t-test statistics since it involved the views of two (2) groups.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the social implication of HIV/AIDS infection on Christian Religious Studies learning disability students in Senior Secondary School Students in Nasarawa State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Opinions of Male and Female Christian Religious Studies learning disability students toward HIV/AIDS Infection and its Social Implication for the Lives of Senior Secondary School Students in Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
People are scared of eating together with HIV/AIDS learning disability students	504	416	6	34	3.45
HIV/AIDS learning disability students lack free association and interaction	354	498	86	22	3.23
People are not free to play games with HIV/AIDS learning disability students	441	365	112	42	3.26
Visitation has reduced on HIV/AIDS learning disability students	424	415	92	29	3.29
HIV/AIDS has promoted relationships for marriages among learning disability students	44	331	488	97	2.34
Some people are scared of attending cultural activities organized by the school with HIV/AIDS learning disability students	514	409	7	30	3.47
Cumulative mean					3.17

Decision mean = 2.50

Results in table 1 show the mean scores of 3.45, 3.23, 3.26, 3.29, 2.34 and 3.47. The cumulative mean is 3.17 which is higher than the decision mean of 2.50 except item 5 that has the mean scores of 2.34. This implies that, Christian Religious Studies students in senior secondary school in Nasarawa state, Nigeria has a negative social implication on the lives of those living with HIV/Aids since people are scared of eating together and attending cultural activities organized by the school with them.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between male and female Christian Religious Studies students in their perception toward HIV/AIDS infection and its social implication on senior secondary school students in Nasarawa state, Nigeria.

Table 2: Independent Samples T-test Opinions of Male and Female Christian Religious Studies learning disability Students on their social implications toward HIV/AIDS Infection and its Social Implication

Variable	N	Mean	SD	T	df	P
Male	546	3.18	.407	1.020	958	.308
Female	414	3.15	.437			

Calculated $p > 0.05$, $t = 1.020$, $df = 958$

Table 2 shows that, $t = 1.020$, $df = 958$, $p = .305 > \alpha = 0.05$. This indicates that the probability value (p) is greater than the alpha level of significance ($p > 0.05$). Therefore, since the p value is greater than the alpha level, the null hypotheses is retained. It therefore, means that, there was no significant difference between male and female Christian Religious Studies students in their perception toward HIV/AIDS infection and its social implication on Senior Secondary School Students in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Discussions

From the analysis of data collected from research questionnaire and hypothesis, it could be said that, majority of the respondents were harmonious in their opinions that, socially, since people are scared of eating together and attending cultural activities organized by the school with them. This finding stresses the potency of the social issues have to do with transformation of society as regards to human relationship that aid in making life easy for man's comfort. This involves the wellbeing of individuals who will aid the enjoyment in the society in all phases of life and civilization. Social issues deal with the description of human society and interaction of individual groups as it affects the welfare of human beings as societal members (Wkye, 2015, Loserian and Jeckoniah, 2018 & Ezra, 2021).

The finding is consistent with the views of Nubed (2016), Usadolo (2019) and Okeorechere (2024) who posit that, the human beings play a vital role in social change. This change can either be positive or negative, depending on the influence. They buttress that, HIV/AIDS have negative impact on the social activities that affect human beings and the entire society. For this reason, the social activities among students in senior secondary schools are highly affected. This is because of the fear of being contacted with the disease. On the same vein, Entonu and Agwale (2019) opine that, sometimes members of the family, class or school mates are scared of eating food and playing games together with those living with HIV/AIDS victims. HIV/AIDS have negatively affected the social activities of humanity and the entire society. This is because, the ailment has led to decline in inter-personal relationship and

association with one another.

Concurring to the above assertions, Awofala and Ogundele (2020) agree with the opinions of Entonu & Agwale (2019) on the damage HIV/AIDs have caused humanity and society socially as many people are afraid to relate and participate in cooperate activities like group learning, physical relationship or snap group pictures. They stressed that, about 65% are stigmatized. Also, Lutala (2019) expresses his dissatisfaction on the negative attitude some people exhibit towards those who are affected with HIV/AIDS. The disease is not a dead sentence as they view it. Dosso (2021), Nsubuga (2024), USAID (2024) and Afolabi (2025) share a similar view that, lack of visitation on those suffering from HIV/AIDS, many have died. They stress that, victims of the ailment are not given fair treatment in the family, church, organizations and the entire society. This has led some of the victims viewing themselves as second class citizens.

On the other hand, Bako, Salihu, Okearu and Ayanti (2017), Wansijiru and Tersa (2025) posit that, HIV/AIDS victims have enhanced friendships and marriages among victims. They stress that, having discovered their status, good number of people joyfully find themselves in relationship that led to marriages and are today happily married with children while NHS (2023), UNAIDS (2024), UNICEF (2024), USAID (2024) and Kikwasi, Lukwale and Mwageni (2024) report that, some married couples living with HIV/AIDS are living happy and comfortable lives in their daily activities than those not affected with the pandemic. They stress for the general public to avoid stigmatization since HIV/AIDs is not a dead sentence.

Conclusion

The finding revealed that, Christian education plays a vital role in the social implications of HIV/AIDS on the social lives of CRS learning disability students in senior secondary schools in Nasarawa state, Nigeria by creating more awareness on the disease and negative social interactions because their lives are affected since students are scared of eating together and attending cultural activities organized by the school with them.

The social life of Christian Religious Studies learning disability students in Senior Secondary School in Nasarawa state, Nigeria has negative implication towards those living with HIV/AIDS infection. This is because they are deprived from having free social life such as fellowship, association, interaction and relationship that could lead to their future marriages, solving some academic issues, and reducing some economic situations hence it has affects them emotionally.

The study creates more awareness on the social life of CRS students in Senior Secondary Schools in the state. Students would not be scared of eating together, playing together and attending cultural activities organised by the school with those Students living with HIV/AIDs infection. It has, for the first time, entirely laid bare that HIV/AIDS infection has negative social implications on CRS learning disability students in Senior Secondary Schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The use of social implications of HIV/AIDS infections on the lives of CRS learning disability students in senior secondary schools in Nasarawa state is highly significant to explain the effects of this disease on the lives of CRS students in senior secondary schools in Nasarawa state.

Recommendations

Based on the finding and conclusion of the study, the following recommendation was made:

- i. CRS teachers should frequently organize counselling on HIV/AIDS awareness among

learning disabilities and rehabilitation CRS Students in order to curb prevalence of the disease.

- ii. Christian religious learners too should assist in creating awareness in the **Church** and society in different level of life among CRS learning disability students on transmission and prevention of HIV/AIDS so as to curb the negative social implication perceived by them in Senior Secondary Schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

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